

Artificial Intelligence

Life and Death in our World

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) is a new leap into a new world of new realities. It has reduced human life to the snap of fingertips. This article focuses on the changes, issues, and new relativity brought by AI in the socio-religious field, including cognition and cosmology, evolution and philosophy, and ethics and law. Socially, AI is the new best buddy of humans because it listens to them and gives them the right solution. AI is a new god who is capable of anything that humans cannot do. In terms of cognition, AI is expected to bring a super-navigational change in people's general thinking spectrum to a highly developed stage that actual people cannot reach. A new multiverse of new dimensions is about to be formed with the AI, where the existence of humans is not certain. Man would be no more man than a robosapien. The general philosophy of humans would be changed into a new artificial philosophy. The human value of virtue would be overturned by the new AI ethics. Justice would be in the new supermind of the AI, where humans' justice has stumbled into the darkness of Hades. Welcome to the new world of AI.

Introduction

Man is the greatest creation ever, but now man is going to be a creator of new life. A god with no godly powers but god to a life processed by codes, digits, and chips. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a reality and is one of the fastest-growing technologies that has a new wave that can bring changes to the whole world like a bullet train does. John McCarthy, a computer scientist who coined the term "artificial

intelligence," was a far-sighted man who could give an apt moniker to the rising battle cry of an intelligence made by man. This era is blessed with all kinds of conveniences provided by AI to lead a carefree life light years away from the stone age. It has opened a new door that leads us to a new universe right in front of us. For instance, the use of AI in medical fields has made humans' lives healthier and stronger.

This article focuses on the changes and issues that AI has brought to every different field, especially in the socio-religious, cognitive, cosmological, evolutionary, philosophical, and even ethical and legal perspectives of the world we live in. AI has introduced new views and new specifications, which have opened a new world of intelligence that can be used without food or fodder.

1. The first cry of artificial intelligence in a social and religious world

"Welcome to the roaring '20s of the 21st century, where this occurs every day in countries around the world. The ferocious behaviours of dictators are enabled by technology that was originally designed with an eye toward human progress and creating a better world."¹

With the introduction of AI, the world has experienced many alterations that have led to the growth of every field from a social perspective. Some of the permanent changes that AI brought are in the fields of health care, transportation, agriculture, military, financial services, education, social sciences, games, tourism, and art. With these changes, man is stepping into an advanced and high-profile life that he has seen only in his dreams.

Mortality is the sole element that makes a man a human being. With the rise of AI, we are on a new track of evolution that would replace everything in a way very different from that of our old lives. When confronted with COVID-19, the AI was able to predict how the deadly disease would spread and also quickly diagnose the disease in a patient.² Thus, AI has deduced that man's involvement in major and critical fields would pose a danger or threat to his precious life.

Driverless cars are becoming increasingly common. A vibrant wave of stimuli was introduced by the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency

¹<https://www.deseret.com/2022/4/26/23033117/the-dark-side-of-ai-disinformation-misinformation-artificial-intelligence-religion-virtual-church>

² Rajiv Malhotra, *Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Power* (India: Rupa, 2021), 28.

(DARPA).³ With these rising waves of human intelligence akin to a tsunami, the world would reach an upgraded level at which people would only have to snap.

AI will automate every field in society, including agriculture, military, and financial services, in a world where social relations of any kind will cease to exist.

The rise of AI has brought the concept of god into a fairytale or fantasy world in which the hero, being god, cannot defeat the villain (AI). "With the rise of AI, the need for god would be less. Soon there would be no gods," says Dan Brown. We are truly in a world where people are forgetting god, and he is becoming a burden to bear. Recently, cults have appeared in the US dedicated to the worship of AI artefacts, if and when they become "super intelligent."⁴ While for some, god is becoming a burden, for others, AI is the new god, who is highbrow and only does good for everyone.

Antony Levandowski, the former engineer of Google and the new CEO of "Way of the Future," is in search of an AI god. Thus, all of these lead to the conclusion that humans, as well as their creations, should be worshiped. Transhumanists are those who believe in AI; they have more direct links back to 18th-century rationalism and humanism.⁵

2. Changes in cognition and cosmology with AI

Man is the dominant being in this world because he has intelligence, and no other animal can compete with him in a steeplechase of aptitude. But now man is seeking a way to transmit his power of cognition to AI, which is his brainchild. "In the context of AI, intelligence is best taken to mean exhibiting interesting behavior."⁶

³ Ibid.

⁴Yorick Wilks, *Artificial Intelligence: Modern Magic or Dangerous Future?* (UK: Icon, 2019).

⁵ Ibid.

⁶Henry Brighton and Howard Selina, *Introducing Artificial Intelligence (Malta: Gutenberg Press, 2003)*, 24.

Intelligence is a kind of heirloom we all possess in this world. It assists us in achieving our goals and objectives within a spectrum through which we can force ourselves to pass. Humans are the ones who are considered to have high potential and to be highly intelligent.

For AI, cognition is computational: they do not have a mind or brain, but everything is computed. This is known as cognitivism.⁷ Because computers and artificial intelligence (AI) cannot express emotions and feelings in the same way that humans do, they have no idea about what sympathy, empathy, anger, and all the other feelings we have are. But these emotions and characters can be computed or fed into their processors or chips so that they can act accordingly, which means they are not conscious of themselves or the surroundings or environment that they are in. They are unable to dream, aim, sleep, or perform other essential human activities.

Since the possibilities of being superhuman are rising, we can say that there is a chance for a world that would be null and void where there is no God, poverty, wars, and conflicts. Thus, AI would constitute a new universe where life would be filled with alacrity. According to Yuval Noah Harari,

Humans are merely tools for creating the internet of all-things which may eventually spread out from planet Earth to pervade the whole galaxy and even the whole universe. This cosmic data processing system would be like God. It will be everywhere and control everything, and humans are destined to merge into it.⁸

With the rise of modern AI, a new culture is going to take birth on this Earth, which is only a spherical planet full of living organisms that are in need of oxygen and carbon dioxide. The new powerful and super-intelligent AI is about to explore a new multiverse, where it will be considered the God almighty, counselor, and problem solver to the non-machine-processed, oxygen-breathing human who is the father of AI generations.

Since there is a chance for the AI god to create a catastrophe in which it could erase humans and build up a new cosmological order, the existence of humans is in doubt. Thus Yuval Noah Harari says, "Homo sapiens will

⁷ Ibid., 35.

⁸ Yuval Noah Harari, *Homo Deus* (UK: Vintage, 2016), 386.

disappear, human history will come to an end, and a completely new kind of process will begin, which people like you and me cannot comprehend."⁹

3. A new evolutionary history with a new world of philosophy

Just think about a world where we have evolved into a new hemisphere where there are no humans but all kinds of robots and cyborgs that have replaced us. Think about the kind of history that they are going to write and circulate in electronic webmails and history texts. They would conclude that evolution has wiped out all living organisms and replaced them with non-natural and ersatz replicas of the living.

In this present era, we are all witnesses to all the innovations that are brought to us within some small moments of precious time that guard us like a rhythmic wind that moves from place to place. The main reason for the evolutions is because of bliss, immortality, and divinity, which hold a grip on humankind, says Yuval Noah Harari.

Transhumanism is a kind of new leap into the world of immortality. The term "transhumanism" was coined by Julian Huxley in 1951. Homo sapiens will evolve into "Robo sapiens," with the actual sapiens only requiring minor upgrades now and then. Humans are going to transmit their cognition into AI and feed it with more and more thinking capacity and intelligence, where everything is going to be turned upside down and humanoids are going to conquer the world, which would end up being a devastating blow to every living being.

Many of the fundamental concepts of AI can be traced back to the work of philosophers such as Descartes, Hobbes, Leibniz, and Ludwig Wittgenstein (1889-1951).¹⁰ According to the philosophers, our world is a totality of truths and facts and is not composed of things. They argued that the world could reach a formal theory that originated from a compilation of formal primitives. This is where the AI translated this perception into a language of symbolic information

⁹ Ibid., 46.

¹⁰ Henry Brighton and Howard Selina, *Introducing Artificial Intelligence*, 138.

processing. With this equipment, the AI would be able to live like a human and do the things he does. AI shares more of its intimacy with philosophy because many of the questions asked by famous philosophers are being answered by the concepts that this intelligent machine is making up and broadening.

According to Aristotle, "philosophic wisdom will contemplate none of the things that will make a man happy, and though practical wisdom has this merit, for what purpose do we need it? Practical wisdom is the quality of mind concerned with things just and noble for man, but these are the things which it is the mark of a good man to do."¹¹ The upcoming AI would have all the virtues that Aristotle states in his famous book "*The Nicomachian Ethics*." Philosophical and practical wisdom would make AI more efficient, easing everything and making people's lives happier and more beautiful.

Humans would lose reason and would submit their entire lives to AI, and thus humans and animals would be equal.

4. The ethics of AI and its legal perspective

On February 28, 2020, the Rome Call for AI Ethics was signed by the Pontifical Academy for Life, Microsoft, IBM, the FAO, and the Italian Ministry of Innovation. The signatories are committed to ensuring the development of an AI that respects the dignity of the human person and that does not have as its sole goal greater profit or the gradual replacement of people in the workplace.¹²

This demonstrates that AI has made a mark in the world of ethics, where they should be abnegative, candid, and friendly. The scientists will use this upgrade to create a perfect creation that will not engage in any vices or improper behavior. As a result, AI will be an ethically moral principle of society that will not exhibit any inequality or gender problems that people currently face.

With the rapidity of the changes, people are going to worship these moral principles brought forward by AI, and they will worship it as a new deity. In October 2021, the Pontifical Council for Culture and the German Embassy to the Holy See hosted a symposium on "The Challenge of

¹¹ Aristotle, *The Nicomachean Ethics*, trans. David Ross (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009), 114

¹² <https://catholicunion.org.uk/2022/01/ai/>

Artificial Intelligence for Human Society and the Idea of the Human Person." One of its speakers, Fr. James Keenan, has written some interesting commentaries, which are:

1. The advances of AI are staggering and more rapid than anyone could have ever anticipated.
2. The discourse on AI is occurring within very different language games.
3. The human being stands as both a contradiction and a mirror to AI.
4. The importance of putting humans at the centre of AI development and use
5. Not all "norm makers" are equal.
6. The present trajectory of AI is a cause of hope and fear.
7. The human inclination to draw lines is reassuring, but humanity is not drawn to concepts.¹³

Ethics and law have a really close relationship because without ethics, law would not exist, and vice versa. According to Paula Boddington, "codes of ethics are nested within the appropriate legal jurisdictions of local, national, and international laws and seek to adhere to these."¹⁴ Technology has grown in such a levitating way that it has towered up to catch up to the heights of legal activities practised by humans.

Dubai Police has taken "Robocop" into its service. This robot can scan everything that is 1.5 metres away and can even speak in six different languages. This way, AI is opening a door in our everyday lives where we can communicate with anyone in times of need or emergency, without language barriers, since the AI is a polymath.

¹³ Ibid.

¹⁴ Paula Boddington, *Towards a Code of Ethics for Artificial Intelligence* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017), 25.

Even in some places, the jurisdiction is taken over by robots. They sentence the verdict according to its intelligence, where the right is rewarded and the wrong is condemned. However, it is possible that it will occur in the other aspect or vice-versa. Let us hope that its jurisdiction would be always correct.

Conclusion

Eagle Eye is a movie by D.J. Caruso. In this film, the AI plays the villain, attempting to kill its creator and his legacy in order to bring its world to Earth. But the protagonist tries hard to stop this intangible and invisible villain with all his might and, at last, saves the world. Thus, this movie shows us the evil side of AI's plan to conquer the world and bring everything under its control.

AI has brought many changes into our lives; it has made difficult aspects of our lives easier and more comfortable zones where we only need to sit and command it to do it for us. Because he has many limitations that he cannot suture up, man is bringing it into every aspect of life. Sharing his brain with his own creation has made many drastic changes; helping him to view galaxies that are light years away from his chair in the room is one of its advantages, and the list goes on endlessly.

Even though it has brought things together in a snap, it has its own disadvantages too. It cannot understand our emotions or converse with itself in the same way that we do. Thus, it is only a programme that can do anything that is fed to it, but there is a possibility that AI can develop its own intelligence and turn against its intelligent creator, man.

Thus let us hope that man's creations do not attack their father, boss, and fellow human beings. May AI only fill in the blanks with potential, rather than coffins full of our own dead bodies.

Bibliography

Books

Aristotle, *The Nicomachean Ethics*, Trans. David Ross Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Brighton, Henry and Howard Selina. *Introducing artificial intelligence. Malta: Gutenberg Press, 2003.*

Boddington, Paula. *Towards a Code of Ethics for Artificial Intelligence*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017.

Malhotra, Rajiv. *Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Power*. India: Rupa, 2021

Wilks, Yorick. *Artificial Intelligence: Modern Magic or Dangerous Future?* UK: Icon, 2019.

Harari, Yuval Noah. *Homo Deus*. UK: Vintage, 2016.

Online Articles

<https://catholicunion.org.uk/2022/01/ai/>

<https://www.deseret.com/2022/4/26/23033117/the-dark-side-of-ai-disinformation-misinformation-artificial-intelligence-religion-virtual-church>.

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